

(70 eV) on a JEOL JMS-DX 300 spectrometer. All melting points are uncorrected.

4-Benzothiazolylazo-N-thiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-5-aminophenylpyrazole: Appropriate derivative of 2-benzothiazolylhydrazonobutyl-1-aminophenyl-1,3-dione^{1*} (0.005 mol) was refluxed with thiosemicarbazide (0.005 mol) in alcohol and acetic acid mixture for 6 h. The product obtained after cooling was filtered and repeatedly recrystallised from DMF and water mixture, m.p. 250° (Found: N 22.12, S, 14.22. C₂₀H₁₉N₇OS₂ calcd. for: N, 22.47, S, 14.64%); λ_{max} (MeOH) 400 nm (-N=N-); M^+ at m/e 437; ν_{max} (KBr) 1590 (N=N), 1610 (C=C or C=N), 1170 (C=S), 3420 (NH) and 750–800 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl). The nmr spectra (CDCl₃ + TFA) of compd. sl. no 20 (Table 1) displayed signals at δ 1.5 (3H, OCH₂CH₃) splitted into a triplet because of the two adjacent hydrogen atoms. Similarly, signals at δ 4.30 (2H, OCH₂CH₂) splitted into a quartet. A sharp singlet at δ 2.5 (3H, CH₃) is observed. Signals at δ 7.30–7.65 slightly upfield (3H, benzothiazolyl ring) spread into two groups due to the inductive effect of -OCH₂CH₃ group. One signal at δ 3.25 (2H, NH₂), one sharp signal at δ 2.8 (1H, NH) and a group of signals at δ 7.5–8.0 (5H, C₆H₅NH) were also observed.

Similarly, other azo compounds, viz. 4-benzothiazolylazo-N-thiocarbamoyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazole, 4-benzothiazolylazo-N-thiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-5-amino-(2-chlorophenyl)pyrazole were prepared by taking suitable hydrazones. Their characteristics are given in Table 1.

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Search for Precocenes in *Ageratum conyzoides* Linn. of North-East India

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PRECOCENE I (2) and **Precocene II (3)** are the first plant anti-juvenile hormones isolated from *Ageratum* (Fam.: Compositae) species that could introduce precocene metamorphosis in insects and are, therefore, potential insecticides¹⁻³. A small annual shrub *A. conyzoides* Linn. and *A. houstonium*⁴ are reported to be good sources for both 2 and 3. It is also reported that while *A. conyzoides* of upper French contains largely a phenolic ester⁵ and that of south India is a source of 2 and a dimer of 3 Bohlman *et al.*⁶ also isolated both 2 and 3 from other Compositae plants. The medicinal importances of *A. conyzoides* such as antitithic⁷, antidysentric⁸ and antibacterial⁹ are reported by several workers. The mode of anti-JH activity¹⁰ and the biosynthesis¹¹ of precocenes are of active interest of several groups.

The potential anti-JH activity of 2 and 3 and lack of data on the presence of these two compounds in different parts of the plant prompted us to undertake this study.

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TABLE 1—GLC ANALYSIS OF OIL OF *A. conyzoides*

Sl no.	Sample no *	Place of collection	Month of collection	% and retention time of		
				1 (4.75) min	2 (12.75) min	3 (25.4) min
1.	RRL-I	Itanagar	Nov. 1983	12.3	3.5	73.0
2.	RRL-M-1	Imphal	Dec. 1983	tr	93.0	tr
3.	RRL-M-2	Imphal	May 1983	1.07	82.7	tr
4.	RRL-J-1	Jorhat	Sept. 1983	12.5	23.3	46.5
5.	RRL-J-2 ^a	Jorhat	Dec 1984	10.4	23.3	55.2
6.	RRL-JF ^b	Jorhat	Dec 1984	6.7	52.0	29.0
7.	RRL-JF ^c	Jorhat	Dec 1984	Nil	6.0	80.0
8.	RRL-M-3	Imphal	March 1985	13.0	51.0	11.0
9.	RRL-J-3	Jorhat	March 1985	13.0	25.0	52.0

*Oil from ^aleaf, ^bflower and ^croot.

Experimental

Extraction of essential oil : In a typical experiment 2.3 kg fresh leaves and twigs of *A. conyzoides* was hydrodistilled to collect 3.25 ml (sp. gr 1.06) of oil.

Column chromatography of oil : The oil (RRL-J) (1 g) was passed through silica gel (26 g) column to obtain 1 (60 mg) (petroleum ether, b.p. 40–46°); 2 (180 mg) (1 : 1, petroleum ether–benzene); and 3 (460 mg) (1 : 4, acetone–benzene); retention time for 1, 4.75, 2, 12.75, and 3, 25.4 min.

Gas chromatographic separation was achieved in 3% OV 225 (on Chromosorb W-HP 80–100 mesh, 2 m × 2 mm i.d. glass) column. A Varian 2440 gas chromatograph with flame ionisation detector and a 1 mV strip chart recorder was used for the analysis. A programmed temperature mode of separation was selected for better elution of the components and the programming mode was set at the following conditions: initial temperature, 130°, holding time 8 min and programmed 2°/min to a final temperature of 160°. The percentage of these compounds were determined by peak area normalisation method.

Results and Discussion

The upper part of the plant (leaf and twig) was collected from the vicinity of RRL, Jorhat (Assam) and its branch laboratories at Imphal (Manipur) and Itanagar (Arunachal Pradesh) and hydrodistilled to collect about 0.14% of essential oil. All these samples were analysed by glc and the result presented in Table 1.

It was observed that *A. conyzoides* from Imphal contains a very high amount of Precocene I (2) than its counterparts at Jorhat and Itanagar. This dominant presence of 2 was found in all the samples from Imphal. We believe that detailed botanical study on this plant from Manipur might reveal interesting results. Kasturi and Manithomas⁴ also isolated 2 but not 3 from the same plant from south India. It was also observed that while the flower

oil had 52% of 2, the leaf oil contained only 23.3% of it, and the root oil was exclusively rich in 3 (80%). Probably precocene I (2) formed in leaf was translocated to flower and root, where it was enzymatically converted to 3 via monooxygenation and subsequent methylation. The oil samples were found to contain a good amount of caryophyllene (1) also.

All the major compounds (1–3) were isolated by column chromatography over SiO₂. While 2 and 3 were identified from the reported spectral data, 1 was identified from spectroscopic analysis and glc retention time with an authentic sample.

It is so far the first report on the glc analysis of the essential oil of *A. conyzoides*.

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